

A CRITICAL ANALYSIS ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION ON SERVICE DELIVERY IN EARLY CHILDHOOD DEVELOPMENT EDUCATION CENTRES IN KENYA

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Abstract:

The study was on critical analysis on the effectiveness of community participation on service delivery in Early Childhood Development Education centers. The main purpose was to critically analyze the effectiveness of community participation on service delivery in ECDE centres in Kenya. The study was meant to train the community as a whole on their roles in the ECDE centres for instance provision of the necessary resources needed at ECDE centres. It was also propose to the policy makers and curriculum developers the need to integrate ECDE centres in education system as in other levels. Five research objectives and questions were also formulated. This study was of significant importance i.e. is to critically analyze the effectiveness of community participation on service delivery in ECDE centres in Kenya. Also, the study was to create awareness among teachers, parents on the importance of their participation on ECDE. It also proposed the policy makers and curriculum developers the need to integrate ECDE centres in education system as in other level. The study adopted qualitative method because it was reliable in generating information. Conclusions and recommendations were drawn on how the immediate community, government and NGOs can ship in to ensure effectiveness of community participation on service delivery in ECDE centres in Kenya.

Keywords: effectiveness, community participation, service delivery

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1. Introduction

Community participation is providing resources in ECDE centres. It is taking responsibility as a society to do their best in understanding that a society to prosper; its members should share that prosperity with full co-operation of its members Olembo (1992). Participation in Early Childhood Education (ECD) is not a new undertaking. Education is a sole duty of the community (Nyerere (1967. Communities provide labor and a time support financially for their institutions. Kenyan communities share the responsibility of financing ECDE centres hand in hand with the government. Community participation is a combined effort by society and its members. This should be done with the full knowledge in that if society prospers, its members with reap the whole benefit. In Kenya factors that hinder community participation of ECD centre may include following among others; poverty, parent's level of education, occupation and family size. Many people in the community know the importance of supporting ECE, KIE (2005).

2. Statement of the Problem

According to the Kenya Education Sector Support Programme (KESSP 2005-2010), the role of parents is that of providing funds for infrastructure, security and healthcare to their children. To achieve the educational goals, the community needs to be involved and actively participate in the implementation, monitoring and actualization of school programmes. The community should be treated as an integral part of the school programmes. This study examined critically the effectiveness of community participation on service delivery in ECDE centres in Kenya.

3. Purpose of the Study

The study critically analyzed the effectiveness of community participation on service delivery in ECDE centres in Kenya. The study was meant to inform the community as a whole on their roles in the ECDE centres for instance provision of the necessary resources needed at ECDE centres. It also proposed to the policy makers and curriculum developers the need to integrate ECDE centres in education system as in other levels.

4. Research Objectives

This study was set to:

1. To critically analyze the effectiveness of community participation on service delivery in ECDE centres in Kenya
2. To critically identify community participation opportunities on service delivery in ECDE centres in Kenya
3. critically analyze the impact of community participation on service delivery in ECDE centres in Kenya
4. To critically analyze hindrances to effective community participation on service delivery in ECD centres in Kenya
5. Critically solutions to hindrances in effective community participation service delivery in the development of ECD centres in Kenya

5. Research Questions

1. To what extend is community participation effective in service delivery to ECDE in Kenya?
2. What are the community participation opportunities on service delivery in ECD centres in Kenya?
3. How does community participation impact on service delivery in ECD centres in Kenya?
4. What are the hindrances to effective community participation on service delivery in the development of ECD centres in Kenya?
5. What are the solutions to hindrances in effective community participation on service delivery in the development of ECD centres in Kenya?

6. Significance of the Study

Involvement of pupils in school activities makes its implementation easy since learners are more receptive. Decision making process enhances co-existence and helps to counter attack the frequent strikes and improved academic performance. Involving parents in school activities helps in budgeting and allocation of funds to meet various expenses incurred by the school. This makes them appreciate the use of resources that they provide hence enabling them provide for resources according to priorities. Community participation strengthens school agents to formulate policies. This motivates the stakeholders in providing the appropriate assistance for improving performance

particularly in exams. Education policymakers have a major role in assisting monitoring and evaluation of policies hence ensuring enhanced and improved curriculum delivery which culminates to quality education among the learners.

7. Critique Literature Review

7.1 Critical analysis the effectiveness of community participation on service delivery in ECDE centres in Kenya

According to Fiore (2011), home is the first place where a child is introduced to the school life by the caregivers. According to Mulatya (2003), educated parents utilize private pre-school learners in a manner that they create pre-school conditions which are more conducive to learners.

7.2. To critically identify community participation opportunities on service delivery in ECDE centres in Kenya

The schools together with the community members represent the major tasks of any school community. This understanding is sensible to citizens and may lead to significant performance in schools. From the literature review, the school administrators restrict the parents and community members to specific roles of provision of resources. There is need to create partnership between the school and the community since none is an island.

7.3. The impact of community participation on service delivery in ECDE centres in Kenya

Good school-community relationship is very fundamental for it ensures that the intended objectives are embraced. Mahoney (2008) argues that every child is a member of a given and particular biological family. Home is the first school .it is very important for it determines the child's future achievement. Parents and relatives in the community should help them do remedial work to boost the pupils to work hard at home and school. Community increases motivation of the learners because being close to them in school. Community helps to prevent behaviors such as truancy and drug taking.

7.4. Critical analysis on what hinders effective community participation on service delivery

Parents and a number of community members earn monthly income of below Kenya shillings 10,000 per month whereas number of teachers on the other hand takes home a monthly income of not above 20,000.00. This implies that majority of parents and

committee members are living below poverty line .They lack motivation to engage actively in development of ECDE centres. Majority of ECD teachers lacks management skills regardless of being equipped with pedagogical skills. This will derail effective service delivery in ECDE centres. This shows that most committee members and community members at large lacked management skills and therefore could not make sound decisions as far as development activities in ECD centres is concerned.

7.5 Solutions to hindrances in effective community participation on service delivery in the development of ECD centres in Kenya

The government should supports people in the community by providing relief food to the families, giving grants to ECDE centres, initiating feeding programs in schools and ensuring that all children under school going age are retained in school during school going days. The government should also provide fertilizers, seeds that are certified to be grown and markets for their products. It should sponsor ECDE training at certificate and degree levels. The government should employ ECDE teachers to reduce the load of paying ECDE teachers by the parents. This will enhance high enrolment in schools and community will participate fully since there were be no other levels associated with ECDE.Non -Governmental Organizations (NGO^s) and other stakeholders through community based organizations (CBO) should make friendly schools in the ECDE centers and this were automatically improve children learning hence development

8. Theoretical Framework

This study adopts community participation theory .Ludwig von Bertallaffy (1968) the proponent. There is the open system and closed systems. A Perfect example of an open system is a school organization because it constantly interacts with its environment. In public primary schools where most of the ECDE centres exist, input and outputs are geared towards achieving some objectives.

9. Research Methodology

The study adopted qualitative method with a critical analysis design because it was found to be reliable in generating factual information. According to Kombo (2006), this method tries to enumerate the social system such as a school. This method is appropriate in this study for deals with educational issues. Schools and communities are social systems which work together for service delivery to be realized.

10. Recommendations

From this critical analysis, the following recommendations were arrived at:

1. The government to sensitize community members on the importance of participating full in ECE programmes and activities.
2. Extension of free primary education services to ECDE level.
3. The government should support people in the community by providing relief food to the families, giving grants to ECDE centres, initiating feeding programs in schools and ensuring that all children under school going age are retained in school during school going days.
4. The government should also provide fertilizers, seeds that are certified to be grown and markets for their products so that community members will harvest quality crops hence reducing poverty levels in Kenya.

11. Conclusion

Parents in most EDCE centres in Kenya and the community at large do not understand the importance of early years of child due to their literacy level-hence their children are deprived the right education. Their growth and development is also impaired since the parents lack the knowledge about balanced diet to children. The researcher found that; teachers and ECDE children in Kenya are not motivated by the community. Motivation is an energizing condition that directs an organism usually towards achieving a certain goal. In abroad sense, motivation is a series of stages which begins with stimulus. The stimulus then triggers a motive which in turn activates and directs behavior. When the teacher is not motivated, he or she cannot interact with children fully. Again children who are not ready or eager to learn hence they are bored, lack interest and inattentive. Since children are not motivated to learn, they miss school unnecessary. Other parents make children to miss school because they do not value the importance of nurturing early years of a child; they are accompanied by the children to go to look for food. Other children are sick due to lack of food and others are even malnourished. Parents and the community should be united and start income generating activities to improve these pathetic situations.

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